

10. Ролевая игра по обслуживанию клиентов: учащиеся разыгрывают сценарий, в котором один учащийся является покупателем, а другой — представителем отдела обслуживания клиентов, отрабатывая навыки общения и решения проблем на изучаемом языке.

Заключение

В заключение, изучение иностранного языка может быть сложным, но также и полезным. Включая различные методы, такие как базовый словарный запас, чтение детских книг, использование онлайн-ресурсов, посещение языковых классов, практика чтения вслух, игра в слова и просмотр телепередач и фильмов, вы можете улучшить свои навыки чтения на языке по вашему выбору. При самоотверженности и практике вы сможете свободно говорить на новом языке и открыть для себя целый мир возможностей.

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COMPUTER ASISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article enables readers to investigate the evolution of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) and its influence in the field of teaching. The implementation of this approach has the potential to increase the motivation and creativity of learners. The paper highlights the importance of teachers possessing

the necessary skills to effectively integrate the CALL program into their classroom instruction. There is ongoing discourse regarding the impact of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) in the field of English Language Teaching (ELT) and the discoveries made by various studies related to the CALL program.

Key words: Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), motivation, creativity, English Language Teaching (ELT).

INTRODUCTION

Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) has been in use for several decades but its importance has grown significantly with the technological advancements of recent years. It has become an effective and powerful tool in all branches of education, including language learning. CALL is the use of technology, including hardware, software, and the internet to enhance teaching and learning in languages. The application of education in language teaching and learning has revolutionized the way educators approach their work.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The history of CALL

CALL is a program derived from CAL (computer-assisted learning), which is implemented in language, but the use of computers here is mainly aimed at providing a language learning tutorial program (Hartoyo 2006, 21).

The origins of CALL can be traced back to the 1960s, when it was initially implemented at Mainframe Computer University. The advent of computer systems in the last decade of the 1970s facilitated the accessibility of information technology to a broader demographic. In 1979, Christopher Evans released his publication titled "The Mighty Micro" under the name of the publishing house Victor Gollancz Ltd. During the early 1980s, there was a surge in the number of published books on CALL. Calico (1982) and EUROCALL (1986) were founded as professional organizations. The 1990s marked the emergence of the World Wide Web, which was made accessible to the general public in 1993. The year 2000 witnessed a significant increase in the accessibility of internet connectivity, thereby

creating novel opportunities for disseminating video and audio content through online platforms such as blogs and podcasting. The year 2004 marked the emergence of the web 2.0 implementation, which delineated significant movements in the utilization of the internet. Pascoe (2011) examines the history of CALL from its inception at the intersection of technological education and second language acquisition, tracing the various paradigmatic changes that have occurred over time.

The impact of CALL in ELT

The use of CALL in English language teaching has had a significant impact on the way learners acquire and develop their language skills. With CALL, learners are not only able to receive instruction on various aspects of the English language but also engage in interactive tasks that aim to reinforce and access their learning. Numerous studies have shown that CALL can improve language competence, increase learner motivation and engagement, promote autonomous learning, and provide opportunities for individualized instruction. In considering the fact that students have constant access to the Internet and employ it for various purposes, it is imperative that educators adopt a receptive stance towards leveraging their students' technological proficiency to integrate it into their instructional practices (Barsotti & Martins, 2011; Gray, Andrew, & Schroeder, 2012). This approach can facilitate a more personalized approach to learning, exceeding the constraints of a conventional classroom setting (Volman, 2005; Larsen-Freeman & Anderson, 2011). The available literature indicates that educators are enthusiastic about incorporating technology into their instructional practices and investigating computer-assisted language learning (CALL) activities. However, the computer-related coursework that they have completed may not necessarily equip them with the necessary skills to effectively implement CALL activities and tasks (Wentworth, 1996; Keirns, 1992; Hargrave & Huse, 2000). According to Chapelle (2006), it is imperative for second-language teachers to possess the ability to select, apply, and occasionally reject technology for the

benefit of their students. Based on Kern's perspective (2011), it is imperative for educators to have an understanding of how modern technology can improve their students' language proficiency. Furthermore, they should be able to discern situations where the use of computers may not be the most effective approach. Egbert (2010) emphasizes that educators must acquire the skills to operate in highly technological settings. This involves evaluating the requirements, preferences, and capacities of students. Incorporating CALL into ELT has several advantages over traditional language teaching methods. It allows learners to access a wealth of online language resources that can support their learning.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, CALL has become an essential tool for English language teaching and offers numerous advantages to teachers and learners. CALL programmers can enhance the way students learn English through various educational technologies and activities. CALL is a concept that benefits both teachers and learners. The potential impact of its utilization in effecting societal change and transformation is significant. In the future, new technological advancements will pave the way for further advancements in the field of CALL.

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ISPAN TILI GRAMMATIKASINI O'RGATISHDA O'YINLARDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Ispan tili grammatikasini o'rgatishda o'yinlardan foydalanishning afzal jihatlari va grammatikani o'rgatishda aynan qanday o'yinlardan foydalanish haqida batafsil to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'yin texnologiyasi, metodika, grammatik o'yinlar, ijodkorlik qobiliyati.

Grammatika bir necha sabablarga ko'ra xorijiy tilni o'rganishda juda muhim. Birinchidan, lug'at boyligi keng bo'lgan til o'rganuvchisi to'g'ri gapirishni, iboralar va gap tuzishni grammatikani bilmasdan turib, o'rganishi mumkin emas. Ammo mohiyatiga ko'ra, grammatika bu shunchaki qoidalar to'plami emas. Uni o'rgatish uchun faqatgina qoidani yodlatish samara bermaydi. Grammatikani o'rgatish uchun albatta o'yin texnologiyasidan foydalanish